

Galaxy evolution in dense environments: a study of the cold ISM in the Fornax cluster

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Often galaxies do not live alone, but in groups or clusters that can harbour up to thousands of galaxies, bound together by a dark matter halo. Galaxies residing in clusters are surrounded by an extremely hot plasma ($T \approx 10^8$ K, e.g., [1]): the “intracluster medium” (ICM). Their relative velocities are high (velocity dispersions are typically several hundreds of km s^{-1}). This means that galaxy clusters are turbulent environments, not unlike swarms of moths attracted to a light source (in this case the brightest cluster galaxy; BCG). As a result, the evolution of cluster galaxies is more complicated than that of their more isolated counterparts. Galaxy clusters harbour a relatively high fraction of elliptical galaxies, suggesting that the star formation (SF) in cluster galaxies is quenched more rapidly than in similar systems in the field (e.g., [2]).

There are various environmental mechanisms that can affect the evolution of cluster galaxies. For example, ram pressure stripping (RPS, [3]) is the “headwind” a galaxy experiences as it moves through the ICM. The ICM can also prevent accretion of fresh gas onto galaxies (e.g. by removing the circum-galactic medium). This is referred to as strangulation/starvation [4]. While field galaxies often merge when they encounter each other, the high velocity dispersion in clusters ensures that most encounters result in relatively brief and violent interactions instead [5]. Even in the absence of violent encounters, the proximity of peers can result in tidal interactions. Both types of interactions can have a severe impact on galaxies’ stellar distributions and interstellar media (ISM).

Exactly how these processes result in the premature quenching of star formation in cluster galaxies is not yet well understood. They are often studied through galaxies’ HI discs, which are very suitable for this because of their wide extent, making them susceptible to environmental effects. However, it is the molecular gas that is the direct fuel for star formation, occupying an important step between the atomic gas phase and actual star formation. If we aim to understand environmental quenching in more detail, it is crucial to study how environmental processes affect the more tightly bound and centrally located molecular gas in cluster galaxies.

The molecular gas content of Fornax cluster galaxies

To this end, we have studied the molecular gas reservoirs of all 30 galaxies in the Fornax cluster that were detected in HI (with the Australia Telescope Compact Array, [6]) or the far infrared (with the *Herschel* Space Telescope, [7]). The Fornax cluster is the smaller but equally nearby sibling of the Virgo cluster ($M = 7 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$, [8] and $D = 19.95$ Mpc, [9]). The $^{12}\text{CO}(1-0)$ line in these galaxies was observed and mapped using the Atacama Millimetre/submillimetre Array [10]. We detected CO in 15/30

galaxies. In 8/15 of these galaxies, the molecular gas is morphologically and kinematically disturbed. Examples of galaxies with regular and disturbed CO emission are shown in figure 3 and 4 of [10], respectively.

In Figure 1, molecular gas fractions of galaxies in the Fornax cluster are compared to a field sample from the Extended CO Legacy Database for GASS (xCOLD GASS, [14]). Fornax galaxies, especially those with disturbed/asymmetric molecular gas reservoirs, are molecular gas deficient compared to xCOLD GASS galaxies. Since the molecular gas discs of Fornax galaxies are also disturbed and/or truncated compared to those of field galaxies, this is likely the result of the environment.

Figure 1: Molecular gas fractions as a function of stellar mass. Black dots represent Fornax galaxies with regular molecular gas reservoirs, whereas red markers indicate galaxies with disturbed molecular gas reservoirs. Triangular markers indicate asymmetric CO emission. Upper limits are shown as magenta open triangles. Within the shaded area, the dashed line represents the median molecular gas fraction from xCOLD GASS. The three shades of grey indicate the 1, 2, and 3 σ levels (from dark to light) of that sample. Outside the shaded area the dashed line is based on linear extrapolation (in log space). Fornax galaxies have systematically lower H_2 fractions than xCOLD GASS galaxies, especially the galaxies with disturbed/asymmetric H_2 reservoirs. This figure includes H_2 fractions from additional data taken with Mopra, shown in cyan. This Figure is an adaptation of Fig. 8 in [10].

The star formation relation in the Fornax cluster

For 9 of the 15 CO detected Fornax galaxies, $\text{H}\alpha$ maps from the Multi Unit Spectroscopic Explorer (MUSE) are available from the Fornax3D project [15], allowing us to calculate the resolved star formation relation (Σ_{H_2} vs. Σ_{SFR} , where Σ_{SFR} is estimated from the $\text{H}\alpha$ emission). This will reveal whether the depletion times of (disturbed) molecular gas reservoirs in Fornax galaxies are affected by environmental processes, or if star formation is (still) as efficient as in field galaxies.

Figure 2: Star formation relation of Fornax cluster galaxies that were detected in both CO and $H\alpha$. The shades of the markers indicate their local densities, determined using Gaussian kernel density estimation (KDE). The dash-dotted lines are lines of constant depletion time. For comparison, the K98 and B08 relations are shown in pink and blue, respectively. Fornax galaxies have normal to short depletion times compared to the K98 and B08 relations. This Figure is an adaptation of Fig. 3 in [12].

The resolved star formation relation of these Fornax galaxies is shown in Figure 2. Here we can see that depletion times of Fornax galaxies ($\Sigma_{H_2}/\Sigma_{SFR}$) are comparable to or slightly shorter than star formation relations from the literature (K98 [16], pink, and B08 [17], blue). This means that the molecular gas in Fornax galaxies is still forming stars at least as efficiently as field galaxies, despite (or perhaps because of) the observed disturbances and deficiencies. The slightly decreased depletion times could be a result of the galaxies experiencing slight starbursts as they enter the cluster.

Molecular gas-to-dust ratios in the Fornax cluster

Dust plays an important role in the star formation process: it catalyses the formation of H_2 , and shields it from radiation. Because dust and molecular gas are linked, we might expect them to be removed from cluster galaxies simultaneously. This has previously been observed in the Virgo cluster [19, 20]. Here we study H_2 -to-dust ratios in the Fornax cluster to investigate whether this is also the case in Fornax.

Dust masses were obtained from SED fits to *Herschel* data from DustPedia (DP, [18]). In Figure 3, H_2 -to-dust ratios are shown as a function of stellar mass, and compared to a field sample and a Virgo cluster sample from DP. Compared to field galaxies, Fornax galaxies have suppressed H_2 -to-dust ratios at fixed stellar mass, whereas those of Virgo galaxies are enhanced. Possible explanations for this include the more efficient stripping

Figure 3: Molecular gas-to-dust ratios of Fornax galaxies compared to the DP sample. DP field galaxies are shown in grey, and DP Virgo galaxies in orange. DP Virgo galaxies inside the virial radius are indicated with larger markers. The median of the DP field sample is indicated with a solid grey line. Markers are similar to those in Figure 1, and explained in the legend. Fornax galaxies have systematically suppressed molecular gas-to-dust ratios, whereas those of Virgo galaxies are systematically increased compared to the DP field sample. This Figure is an adaptation of Fig. 3 in [13].

of H_2 compared to dust, and the more efficient enrichment of dust in the star formation process compared to H_2 in the Fornax cluster.

Fornax cluster galaxies detected in CO are systematically H_2 deficient compared to field galaxies at fixed stellar mass, and half of them have disturbed H_2 reservoirs. However, this gas is still forming stars at least as efficiently as field galaxies. H_2 -to-dust ratios are suppressed, suggesting that either molecular gas is affected more strongly by environmental effects than dust, or that dust is replenished more efficiently in the SF cycle.

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